

Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydropyrido (4,3-b) Indoles using Polyphosphate Ester as a Cyclising Agent¹

SHIVAYOGI P. HIREMATH* and MURALIDHAR G. PUROHIT

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwar-580003.

Manuscript received 1 August 1975 ; accepted 24 November 1975

Methyl substituted ethyl indole-2-carboxylates have been converted into the corresponding β -(indol-2-yl) ethylamines (isotryptamines) through indole-2-carboxaldehydes. These amines are subjected to benzoylation to get the respective amides, which in turn on cyclisation with PPE give 1-phenyl-3,4-dihydropyrido(4,3-b) indoles (γ -carbolines) in good yield.

WE have shown that N_2 -acyl or aryl isotryptamines easily undergo Bischler-Napieralski synthesis, in the presence of polyphosphate ester (PPE), to yield 3,4-dihydropyrido(4,3-b) indoles (γ -carbolines) in good yields.^{2,3} Recently, we have also demonstrated that PPE could be used with advantage, for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrido(3,4-b)-benzindoles (β -carbolines).⁴ In continuation of our above work and in order to test the generality of the use of PPE as an acidic cyclising agent, we now report the synthesis of methyl substituted 3,4-dihydropyrido(4,3-b)indoles.

Ethyl 5-methylindole-2-carboxylate (*1a*) was prepared according to the literature method.⁵ It was subjected to LAH reduction in a mixture of ether and THF to get 2-methylindole-2-methanol (*1b*) in good yield (96%). The alcohol (*1b*), on oxidation with manganese dioxide in dichloromethane, yielded 5-methylindole-2-carboxaldehyde (*1c*) which on condensation with nitromethane and subsequent reduction of the product (*1d*) with LAH in dry benzene-ether yielded 5-methyl- β -(indol-2-yl)ethylamine (*1e*). Following a similar sequence of the reactions, 4,7-dimethyl- β -(indol-2-yl)ethylamine (*2e*) and 5,7-dimethyl- β -(indol-2-yl)ethylamine (*3e*) were prepared. These were then reacted with benzoyl chloride in presence of sodium hydroxide to get the respective amides (*4,5,6*). The amides on cyclisation with PPE⁷ in chloroform furnished the corresponding 1-phenyl-3,4-dihydropyrido(4,3-b)indoles (*7,8,9*).

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|---|-----------------------------------|----------------------|
| 1 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = H$ | a - $COOC_2H_5$ |
| 2 | $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = H, R_3 = CH_3$ | b - CH_2OH |
| 3 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = CH_3$ | c - CHO |
| | | d - $CH=CH-NO_2$ |
| | | e - $CH_2-CH_2-NH_2$ |

- | | |
|---|-----------------------------------|
| 4 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = H$ |
| 5 | $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = H, R_3 = CH_3$ |
| 6 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = CH_3$ |
| 7 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = H$ |
| 8 | $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = H, R_3 = CH_3$ |
| 9 | $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = CH_3$ |

The ir spectrum of compound (*4*) exhibits NH and C=O absorption at 3420m, 3340s, and 1660s cm^{-1} , while compound (*7*) showed the presence of NH absorption at 3450 cm^{-1} only and the absence of C=O absorption. The above fact indicates that the cyclisation has taken place at position-3 of indole molecule. Further this is supported by the nmr spectra⁸ of compounds (*4* and *7*). The nmr spectrum of compound (*4*) showed the resonances due to the phenyl, NH and 3, 4, 6, 7 protons in the region 2τ to 4τ . The high field singlet ($3-7\tau$) having fair intensity is assigned to free NH proton, present in the side chain. The broad absorption at 3.4 may be due to indole NH. Out of the remaining nine protons, five are from sparsely occupied phenyl group and four are from 3, 4, 6 and 7 position of indole molecule (2.4τ to 3.1τ). The methylene protons present in the side chain give rise to two triplets in the region 6.2τ to 6.85τ . The singlet at 7.5τ is due to the free methyl group attached at position 5 of the indole molecule. In the nmr spectrum of compound (*7*), six protons, out of nine aromatic protons in the region 2.4τ to 3.5τ , represent the less sterically hindered phenyl group and NH of the pyrrole residue. These two give rise to multiplet at 2.6τ . The remaining three aromatic protons present at position 6, 7 and 9 of the compound (*7*), give rise to three signals at 2.8τ , 3.0τ and 3.2τ . The remaining part of the spectrum is analogous to that of compound (*4*).

* For correspondence : Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University Post-graduate Centre, Sedam Road, Gulbarga-585105.

Experimental

The ir spectra were recorded on Carlzeis Ur-10 spectrometer. The nmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal reference at 60 MC. PPE was prepared according to the literature method⁷. Only the general methods for the experimental procedures are given.

1. *Indole-2-methanols (1b, 2b and 3b)*: To a suspension of LAH (0.8 g, 0.021 mole) in dry ether, a solution of appropriate ethyl indole-2-carboxylates (0.021 mole) in a mixture of dry ether (25 ml) and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml), were added at a rate sufficient to maintain gentle refluxing. The solution was stirred for another 2 hr, then decomposed with water and sodium hydroxide (15%). The resulting product was filtered, the filtrate on removal of the solvent yielded indole-2-methanols which are described in Table 1.

2. *Indole-2-carboxaldehydes (1c, 2c and 3c)*: To a solution of indole-2-methanols (0.009 mole), in dichloromethane (115 ml), activated manganese dioxide (6g) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 35-40 hr. After filtration, the residual manganese dioxide was thoroughly washed with excess of dichloromethane. The combined filtrate and washings were evaporated to get indole-2-carboxaldehydes (Table 1).

3. *2-(2'-Nitrovinyl)indoles (1d, 2d and 3d)*: A solution of indole-2-carboxaldehydes (0.002 mole) and nitromethane (3g, 0.055 mole) in methanol (50 ml) was cooled to -5° and sodium hydroxide (50%, 15 ml) was added dropwise with stirring maintaining the temperature below 0° when a bulky white precipitate rapidly separated. After an hr. ice water (50 ml) was added, the resulting product was slowly added to a stirred mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (65 ml) and ice (240 g). The crude product which separated as brownish orange solid was collected, dried and crystallised (Table 2).

4. *β -(Indol-2-yl) ethylamines (1e, 2e and 3e)*: A solution of 2-(2-nitrovinyl)indoles (0.009 mole), in dry benzene (20 ml), was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of LAH (3 g, 0.078 mole) in dry ether (100 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 20-22 hr. After cooling, the excess of LAH was decomposed by the addition of sodium hydroxide (15%) and water. It was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation yielded β -(indol-2-yl) ethylamines as semi-solid which were characterised as their benzoyl derivatives.

5. *N_2 -Benzoyl- β -(indol-2-yl)ethylamines (4, 5 and 6)*: β -(Indol-2-yl)ethylamine (0.0072 mole) was taken in a conical flask, benzoyl chloride (2 ml, 0.013 mole) and sodium hydroxide (10%, 40 ml) were added to it. The mixture was shaken, with occasional cooling, for

TABLE 1

m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$) Nature (solvent)	<i>1b</i> 119-120° Colourless needles (benzene)	<i>2b</i> 95 Colourless plates (benzene)	<i>3b</i> 149° Colourless needles (benzene)	<i>1c*</i> 175 Light yellow plates (ethanol)	<i>2c</i> 197 Brown coloured flakes (ethanol)	<i>3c</i> 178 Straw coloured needles (ethanol)
Found (%)	C 74.2 H 6.5 N 8.5	C 75.2 H 7.5 N 8.0	C 75.7 H 7.0 N 8.0	C 75.6 H 5.7 N 9.0	C 76.0 H 6.3 N 8.4	C 76.2 H 6.4 N 7.9
Mol.formula	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}$	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}$	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}$	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$
Calc. (%)	C 74.5 H 6.9 N 8.7	C 75.4 H 7.4 N 8.0	C 75.4 H 7.4 N 8.0	C 75.4 H 5.8 N 8.9	C 76.3 H 6.4 N 8.1	C 76.3 H 6.4 N 8.1
Yield (%)	96	99	96	77	87	77

* Lit.⁹ m.p. 175°

TABLE 2

m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$) Nature (solvent)	<i>1d</i> 185° Brownish orange plates (benzene)	<i>2d</i> 215 Brownish orange needles (benzene)	<i>3d</i> 237 Brownish orange needles (methanol)	<i>4</i> 161-162 Colourless needles (ethanol)	<i>5</i> 225 Colourless needles (aq. ethanol)	<i>6</i> 258 Colourless needles (ethanol)
Found (%)	C 65.1 H 5.1 N 13.5	C 66.9 H 5.8 N 13.1	C 66.8 H 5.4 N 13.1	C 78.0 H 6.4 N 9.9	C 78.0 H 6.5 N 9.8	C 78.2 H 6.7 N 9.6
Mol.formula	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}$
Calc. (%)	C 65.3 H 5.0 N 13.8	C 66.7 H 5.6 N 13.0	C 66.7 H 5.6 N 13.0	C 77.7 H 6.5 N 10.0	C 78.0 H 6.9 N 9.6	C 78.0 H 6.9 N 9.6
Yield (%)	72	63	72	75	60	75
IR cm^{-1}	NH 3350s	—	—	NH 3420m 3340s C=O 1660s	NH 3400b C=O 1680s	NH 3400b C=O 1690

TABLE 3

	7	8	9
m.p. (°C)	300	320	292
Nature (solvent)	Brown coloured plates (chloroform)	Brown coloured flakes (chloroform)	Brown coloured flakes (chloroform)
Found (%)	C 82.7 H 6.3 N 11.0	C 83.0 H 6.7 N 10.3	C 83.1 H 6.6 N 10.3
Mol. formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ ⁻	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂
Calc. (%)	C 83.0 H 6.2 N 10.8	C 83.2 H 6.6 N 10.2	C 83.2 H 6.6 N 10.2
Yield (%)	67	68	58
IR cm ⁻¹	NH 3440m	NH 3430m	NH 3440s

about 30-40 min. It was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The N₂-benzoyl-β-(indol-2-yl)ethylamine separated was filtered and crystallised (Table 2).

6. *1-Phenyl-3, 4-dihydropyrido (4, 3-b)indoles* (7, 8 and 9): A solution of the corresponding amides (4, 5 and 6) (0.0012 mole) and PPE (2.5 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. After removal of the solvent in *vacuo*, cold water was added to the reaction mixture under ice cooling. It was stirred for 2 hr. to effect the complete decomposition of the reagent. The solution was washed with ether to remove the non-basic material and aqueous layer made alkaline with sodium hydroxide (10%). The product thus liberated was extracted with ether, dried and evaporated to get 1-phenyl-3, 4-dihydropyrido (4, 3-b)indoles (Table 3).

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Messrs V. A. Desai and G. S. Gadaginamath for microanalysis.

References

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